

Towards Digital Twins with Wearables: A Fully Data-driven Causal Analysis of Lifestyle Effects on Sleep Biomarkers

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Abstract text

Introduction: Over the past decade, mobile and wearable devices have seamlessly integrated into daily life, offering researchers unprecedented opportunities to analyze lifestyle habits. Continuous unobtrusive monitoring with wearables, combined with user input and contextual information collected over time, enables the exploration of complex relationships in multi-source data. These new data streams offer valuable insights into how lifestyle factors, such as alcohol intake and stress, interact with sleep. While previous studies have established associations, causal relationships remain unclear. To identify modifiable risk factors and guide effective interventions for improving sleep quality, it is essential to uncover the underlying causal mechanisms. In this work, we apply data-driven causal inference methods to estimate the effects of lifestyle factors on sleep, laying the groundwork for personalized digital twin prototypes that support lifestyle simulations and intervention design.

Materials and methods:

Data collected over 30 days by 294 participants with wearables were aggregated daily, combined with contextual information from questionnaires and weather data, resulting in an analytical sample of 277 individuals. The wearable-derived metrics included active time, average stress, heart rate, and sleep-related measures such as resting heart rate, proportions of sleep stages, sleep score, and other sleep-derived biomarkers. We used causal discovery algorithms to construct a Maximal Partially Directed Acyclic Graph (MPDAG), initialized with a temporally ordered PC algorithm and refined with the Structural Expectation-Maximization algorithm. Bootstrapping ensured stability, while background knowledge on temporal ordering and exogeneity was incorporated. Adjustment sets for each research question were derived through the Intervention with DAG Absent (IDA), which identifies valid local adjustment sets for causal effect estimation. Causal effects were then estimated using linear mixed-effects models to account for inter-individual variability.

Results:

Causal discovery on the data from 80% of the participants yielded a lifestyle structure consistent with literature. Estimated causal effects (95% CI) on the hold-out set of 56 participants showed that alcohol intake decreased REM sleep percentage by either -4.76 ($-6.02; -3.49$) or -4.17 ($-5.45; -2.90$), corresponding to the two valid IDA-derived adjustment sets compatible with the MPDAG. Daily stress reduced REM percentage by -0.22 ($-0.25; -0.18$), and total sleep time increased the sleep score by 4.85 ($4.25; 5.45$). Random intercepts indicated significant inter-individual variability, highlighting personal differences across participants.

Conclusions:

In this work, we showed that causal discovery methods can be exploited with longitudinal lifestyle data, enabling the identification of meaningful mechanisms. Further analysis aiming to understand individual-level effects revealed differences between participants, underscoring the value of personalization. Learned causal effects represent a foundation for constructing digital twins - personalized, computational representations of individuals that evolve with data. By enabling counterfactual reasoning (e.g., "What if I slept more?"), these models can simulate the impact of lifestyle changes before interventions are implemented and help inform patients and healthcare professionals. This supports the development of adaptive systems for behavioral coaching and health optimization, with the possibility of incorporating also reinforcement learning enhanced personalization. Future work will focus on extending the presented methodology with longer observation periods to uncover personalised behavioral insights.

General

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